

THE IMPORTANCE OF LINGUACULTURAL ANALYSIS

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Abstract: The issue of the relationship between language and culture has always dragged the scholars' attention. According to the American linguist E. Sepir (1993), language is closely connected with culture, which develops, expresses, and serves as a basis for the development of culture. It is known that language is in constant motion, it is an integral part of the history and culture of certain speakers, a mirror of the nation, the culture of the people. "Because any culture is manifested in language, it finds its material shell in language, and it develops and changes under the influence of the environment. The cultures of different nations differ from each other, first of all, in how they assimilate reality materially and spiritually." The need to study the national and cultural features of language units and the need to shed light on the relationship between language and culture led to the formation of linguaculturology as a separate field. In particular, the fields of linguaculturology and translation theory work together to develop the principles of translation of language units with national and cultural features.

Keywords: Linguacultural, phraseologism, linguaculturema, realities, archetypes, paremiological, linguistic, comparative study, cultural realities, linguaculturologic algorithmization national-cultural feature lexical-semantic.

It is well known that the peoples of the world differ from each other in terms of their history, socioeconomic development, cultural development, and way of life. Every nation has its own dress culture, customs, traditions, and manners. The expression of such national and universal values in any work reflects the uniqueness of that nation. In this sense, "linguistic means that reflect the concepts, things, and events specific to a particular people, nation and ethnic group are the main means of determining the national character of a work of art." In the process of translation, these peculiarities, pictorial differences in different languages, and in some cases similarities, become clear.

The connection between language and culture and the reflection of national-cultural identity in the translation is crucial. The transmission of the worldview from one language to another, combined with cultural and spiritual features, depends on the quality and effectiveness of the translation. After all, when work in one language is translated into another, not only its meaning is expressed, but also the social origin, history, culture, and worldview of that people are promoted. In this regard, G. Salomov (1966) noted that "It is difficult to imagine how nations can establish friendly relations with each other, study and master each other's cultural riches without translation." An analysis of the literature on this topic shows that, as units of language with national-cultural features, mainly reality and phraseology are recognized in them.

Studies give different descriptions of realities. For example, realities consist of words that express specific objects, concepts, and realities, moreover they relate to history, life, and the culture of a particular nation. They are unique to one language, have no alternatives in other languages, and also require the use of special methods in the translation process. Realities

have entered the theory of translation as an independent unit and play an important role in translating the national and historical peculiarities of language. R.Fayzullaeva (1972) also studies the problems of national color in translation on the example of German and Uzbek languages. Realities appear in the language of one nationality, reflect the way of life, history, and culture of the nation, and in another language, there is no clear alternative.

All the elements that make up a work of art, the spirit of the period, and the behavior and circumstances of the characters are shining examples of the national-cultural environment of that nation. M.Javburiev (1991) also noted that each work of art has its own time and place, the specificity of time and place are inextricably linked with the image of the writer in his actions, he admits that his speech is manifested in his originality. So, these and other aspects reflect the spirit of the period and the historical landscape, historical-national features in the work. Admittedly, another means of reflecting national-cultural identity is phraseological and pharmacological units. Phraseological units, which are the expression of the beauty and art of language, are not only means of expressing the imagery of language but also reflect the national culture, specific character, humor, sorrows, and concerns, as well as the mentality of the people. Therefore, in the literary text, phraseology is widely used to fully reveal the subtleties of the characters, to illustrate, exaggerate the description of events and situations. In the semantic structure of the phraseology of each language, there are socio-historical events, moral and cultural norms, the spiritual world and religious ideas of the nation, national traditions, and customs. The effective and appropriate use of such units in the play ensures the popularization of the language of the work.

Linguaculture is also a set of forms of language symbols, the content and cultural meaning of which are reflected in this symbol. It has a much deeper meaning than the word and has a more complex structure than the original language units. "Linguaculturema", in addition to linguistic perceptions (forms of the meaning), incorporates extralinguistic states in constant motion, and cultural appearances (realities, lacunae). Regarding the meaning of linguocultures, O. Yusupov (2011) says: "The semantics of linguaculturema includes words, phraseological units, phrases, sentences, speech clichés, complex syntactic units, texts, etc., reflecting a part of the culture." Thus, linguaculturema is a unit specific to a particular people, covering linguistic and non-linguistic factors, expressing the interdependence of language and culture, which can be manifested in all means of language. It can consist of a single word (wedding, soup), compound words (Uzbek dance, hospitality, tea party, etc.), or a whole paragraph or text. Consequently, linguaculturema has its own complex structure, and each linguaculturema has primary (semantic) and secondary (nonlinguistic) meanings. According to Vorobev's (2008) method of analysis, first, the semantic aspect of linguaculturema as a lexeme is determined (lexicographical analysis using dictionaries). In the next stage, based on the semantic analysis, the linguistic units (paremiological and phraseological units, realities, stylistic means, etc.) related to the non-linguistic aspect, which combine materialspiritual and national-cultural features, are studied. Explanatory, ethnographic, and It seems that the linguaculturological approach plays an important role in the theory and practice of translation, and the complexities of translating linguacultures and ways to solve them have not been sufficiently studied in the monographic plan on the basis of modern approaches. Based on our observations, we propose the following step-by-step approach to the adequate representation of linguacultures in translation: 1. Comparative conceptual analysis of

linguaculture before translation. 2. The correct choice and appropriate use of lexical-phraseological means of translation (equivalent, alternative and descriptive methods) in the translation of linguaculturalism. 3. Analysis of synonyms and antonyms in the translation of linguaculturems and their correct use. 4. Analysis and appropriate reflection of phraseological units and stylistic means in maintaining the emotional sensitivity and imagery of linguacultures in translation. 5. Proper translation of linguacultures with a correct understanding of the linguistic landscape of the original language, taking into account the explicit and implicit data, as well as the modal attitude of the author. Another linguaculturema is that when we take this happiness, the word happiness sounds different in every language and nations have always expressed their attitude toward this concept. Linguaculture of happiness is a universal concept, which reflects a number of national and cultural features in each language.

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